

**ADVANCED METHODS AND STEPS OF PROFESSIONAL
PROFESSIONAL IMPROVEMENT OF COACHING BASED ON
INNOVATIVE APPROACHES****Yarkinay Nurumbekova Anarmatovna**

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Future professionals reflect deeply, combining their experiences, feedback, and personal insights to develop their own unique coaching style. Even after formal education, Continuous learning, lifelong learning and professional development are essential. Attendance at workshops, training seminars, and subsequent certifications ensures that a trainer stays at the top of their game.

Thus, the formation of coaching competence in future professionals is a multifaceted process that includes various components and stages and follows several principles. Understanding these aspects is critical to designing and implementing effective coaching competency development programs. This will be the basis for the next part of this dissertation, which will explore innovative methods of coaching competence formation in future professionals.

The foundation of any professional field is often based on principles, methodologies, and foundations derived from extensive research and cultural understanding. This applies especially to the field of coaching skills in the training of future specialists. It is noteworthy that both Uzbek and Russian literature have deep views on this matter¹.

Russian author Kuznetsov, in his important work on the psychology of coaching, distinguishes three main components of coaching competence: knowledge, skills and attitude. Uzbek researcher Mirzakhmedov complements this point of view by highlighting the cultural nuances in the development of competence, especially as seen in the context of Central Asia.

The components of coaching competency are: Knowledge: This focuses on understanding the underlying theories and practices of coaching. Russian sources such as Petrov and Ivanova document the evolution of coaching theories over time and their relevance in contemporary Russian society².

Skills: Just knowing is not enough; application is important. As noted in the works of Umarov from Uzbekistan, practical methods and strategies are of decisive importance.

Attitude: The fine art of creating a comfortable coaching environment is often based on the right mindset. This echoes in the works of the Russian writer Sidorova and the Uzbek writer Rahmonov.

Principles of coaching competence

1. Coaching and training: practical methods and techniques G. E. Parslow, M. Ray. — SPb.: Peter, 2003. — 103-104 p.: il. — (Series "Practicheskaya psychology").

2. Whitmore John: Coaching. Basic principles and practical coaching in leadership. 2019.-220-221s

Some basic principles of coaching reflected in Uzbek and Russian literature is based on Customer-centric approach: A principle widely discussed by Sobirov of Uzbekistan. This emphasizes the importance of placing the client at the center of the coaching relationship. Continuous learning: As documented by the Russian scholar Morozov, the coach's journey is one of constant learning and adaptation³.

Stages of formation of coaching competence.

Competence in coaching does not appear overnight. There are distinct stages in this evolution. Awareness: Understanding the need and role of coaching. This is discussed in detail in the works of Russian authors such as Volkov. Learning: Deep penetration into coaching theories and methodologies. An example of this is extensive research conducted by Uzbek academician Navrozov. Practice: implementation of knowledge in real-world scenarios. Both Zufarov from Uzbekistan and Likhachev from Russia gave many examples in this regard. Mastery: When coaching becomes an intuitive process. The Uzbek author Nurmatov beautifully covers the journey to mastery⁴.

Competency-based coaching is an advanced method of professional development, emphasizing the formation of specific skills and knowledge in future professionals. This approach recognizes the multifaceted nature of competence and includes different dimensions such as knowledge, skills, attitudes and values. The main goal is to develop a learning culture that is dynamic, flexible and active in nature.

Knowledge: This covers the coachee's understanding of the theories, models and components that underpin coaching practice. It also includes understanding organizational culture, dynamics, and the specific context in

which coaching takes place. Coaching knowledge is the foundation on which coaching practice is built, and it creates a basis for the functioning of the coach.

Skills: Skills refer to the ability to apply knowledge in practical situations. In the context of coaching, it encompasses a wide range of skills such as effective communication, active listening, questioning, feedback and conflict resolution. In addition, coaching skills include the ability to develop and implement effective coaching plans and strategies.

Today, doubts about the importance and role of coaching as a form of social practice and profession are becoming less and less. While maintaining his originality, he settled on the border between psychotherapy and business consulting.

However, despite significant advances and three decades of experience, coaching as a discipline is still fragmented and unrecognized. Coaching today is more a collection of work models, theories, practices, methods and methods proposed by different authors with different backgrounds and perspectives. Analyzing many sources, V. Brock comes to the following conclusion: coaching is experiencing the same fragmentation phenomena characteristic of modern society, knowledge and science⁵.

3. Ya.A. Nurumbekova Personal psychology and coaching manual. Gulistan. GulDU.2022.-121-122b

4. Whitmore John: Coaching. Basic principles and practical coaching in leadership. 2019.-135-136s

5. Ya.A. Nurumbekova Personal psychology and coaching manual. Gulistan. GulDU.2022.-171-172b

R. Biswas-Dener and B. Dean describe this as the paradox of coaching: the profession systematically helps people reach their potential.

helps, but cannot fully realize its potential and remains in a kind of "professional infancy". It is losing its consistency, unified definitions, uniform content of the curriculum and a set of common activities: some trainers work with inspirational stories and games, others are more assessment-oriented, and still others are focused on goals. and focuses on behavior (ibid.).

It is important to take into account many aspects that serve the effective development of this field as part of an innovative approach to improving the mechanism of training competence of future specialists⁶.

In today's world, it is becoming fashionable not only to have a "psychological friend" to turn to in difficult situations, but also to have a coach-

mentor who can help you be more effective in your personal and professional life. The metaphor of a coach-coach, which has been actively introduced not only in sports, but also in business, career growth and daily activities, has turned out to be extremely effective and attractive.

However, there is a contradiction between the diversity of approaches and methods in coaching and the pursuit of unity and integrity in this field. It seems that psychotherapy has moved from conflict and conflict to the recognition and acceptance of different approaches and methods. However, the main difference is that psychotherapy has philosophical foundations, concepts and general methodological principles from the very beginning, which the coach does not yet have. It should be noted that one of the trends in the historical development of coaching was its separation from psychology and psychotherapy. This allowed coaching to stand out as an independent practice,

but this approach made it less dependent on psychological concepts and methods.

The process of becoming a coach is a synthesis of emerging practices, innovative ideas and original methods from psychotherapy.

The history of the coach emphasizes the importance of connecting with psychology and psychotherapy, especially in the early stages. The starting point was the development of practices, innovative ideas in psychotherapy, as well as original methods. This shows that coaching and psychology have wide areas of communication that help to develop a more balanced and fundamental approach to the formation of coaching competence of future professionals.

The connection between coaching and psychology is obvious. When work is accompanied by motivation, goals, feelings, images, subjective time, psychological resources, relationships, then it intersects with the field of psychology. This applies to both life coaching and business coaching, where organizational structure, management, leadership and performance are also considered. In order to improve the mechanism of formation of coaching competence of future specialists based on an innovative approach, it is necessary to study the relationship between coaching and psychology in depth. The integration of modern psychological theories and approaches can help develop a more sustainable and deeper coaching practice. In order to improve the mechanism of formation of coaching competence of future specialists on an innovative basis, it is necessary to focus on updating the theoretical foundations on which coaching practice is built. There is a need for deeper analysis and integration of contemporary psychological research within this field.